

Test.O Framework Assessment Questionnaire - Coordinators

This questionnaire aims to collect information about the experience of Coordinators onboarding with the Test.O framework.

* Obrigatória

* Este formulário registrará seu nome. Preencha-o.

1. You are being invited to participate in the research project: About the Test.O framework, a framework used to integrate new employees into distributed testing teams, whose responsible researcher is anonymous.

The objectives of the questionnaire are: Verify whether Test.O is efficient as an onboarding framework.

You have complete freedom to refuse participation or withdraw your consent, at any stage of the research, without any penalty for the treatment you receive in this service from team X of the anonymous Institute.

If you agree to participate, your participation will consist of an interview and filling out a form about the Onboarding process of team x, both accompanied by the person responsible for the research.

All research with human beings involves risks to participants. In this research, as it is an interview, there are no risks.

The following benefits are also expected from this research: pointing out the positive points of having an onboarding process, validating the Test.O framework.

If you consider it necessary, you will have time to reflect on your participation, consulting, if necessary, your family or other people who can help you make a free and informed decision. (Res. 466/2012-CNS, IV.I.c)

Agree

Disagree

2. We guarantee that you will maintain the confidentiality and privacy of your participation and data during all phases of the research and subsequently in scientific dissemination (Item IV.3.e, of CNS Resolution No. 466 of 2012).

You can contact the responsible researcher at any time.

- Agree
- Disagree

3. How long have you worked with software testing? *

- Less than 1 year
- Until 3 year
- Until 4 year
- Until 5 year
- More than 5 year

4. How long have you been a onboarding coordinator? *

- Less than 1 year
- Until 3 year
- Until 4 year
- Until 5 year
- More than 5 year

5. Do you consider the onboarding process for new employees important in times of distributed software testing? Why? *

6. What characteristics do you identify in test teams without an onboarding process? *

7. What characteristics do you identify in testing teams with an onboarding process? *

8. This scale consists of a number of words that represent different feelings and emotions. Read each item and indicate to what extent you felt this way, in your activities as coordinator of the Onboarding process. *

	extremely	quite a bit	moderately	a little	very slightly or not at all
interested	<input type="radio"/>				
distressed	<input type="radio"/>				
excited	<input type="radio"/>				
upset	<input type="radio"/>				
strong	<input type="radio"/>				
guilty	<input type="radio"/>				
scared	<input type="radio"/>				
hostile	<input type="radio"/>				
enthusiastic	<input type="radio"/>				
proud	<input type="radio"/>				
irritable	<input type="radio"/>				
alert	<input type="radio"/>				
ashamed	<input type="radio"/>				
inspired	<input type="radio"/>				
nervous	<input type="radio"/>				
determined	<input type="radio"/>				
attentive	<input type="radio"/>				
jittery	<input type="radio"/>				
active	<input type="radio"/>				
afraid	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Do you consider that the Test.O framework helps onboarding new employees into distributed testing teams? *

Yes

No

10. Would you recommend the Test.O framework process to other distributed testing teams?
Why? *

11. What do you consider positive about the Test.O Onboarding process? *

12. What do you consider negative about the Test.O Onboarding process? *

13. Complete the sentence:

"Being a coordinator and using Text.O framework for the onboarding process makes me
....." *

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